

HERCCULES
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Dissemination and Communication Package – RP1

Deliverable D10.2

Date: 30th June 2024

Funded by
the European Union

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D10.2_Dissemination and Communication Package – RP1

Deliverable title Work Package Lead beneficiary Due Date Actual delivery date Dissemination level Abstract	Dissemination and Communication Package – RP1 WP10 EUCORE 30/06/2024 (M18) 28/06/2024 Public This deliverable summarises the dissemination and communication activities carried out throughout the first reporting period of the HERCCULES project.
Project Acronym Project Call Type of Action Project Start Date Project duration Grant Number	HERCCULES HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01-15 HORIZON EUROPE - Innovation Action 01/01/2023 60 months 101096691

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HISTORY OF CHANGES

VERSION	DATE	MODIFICATION	PREPARED BY (Main contributors)	APPROVED BY
1	28/06/2024	Initial version	EUCORE - Martina Fantini - Irene Liverani - Melisa Borré - Roberto Di Gioacchino - Roberto Cippitani	- LEAP (Project Coordinator) - All Consortium
2				
3				

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION.....	6
2	LOGO	7
3	TEMPLATES	10
4	PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS.....	13
5	WEBSITE.....	20
6	PUBLICATIONS	28
7	PROJECT DISSEMINATION EVENTS.....	31
8	PARTICIPATION IN EXTERNAL EVENTS	34
9	LIAISON ACTIVITIES	39
10	SOCIAL MEDIA.....	43
11	PRESS RELEASES AND OTHER MASS MEDIA	46
12	NEWSLETTERS.....	51
13	ADDITIONAL COMMUNICATION MATERIAL	53

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ACRONYMS USED TO IDENTIFY CONSORTIUM MEMBERS

REF.	ORGANIZATION	ACRONYM
B1	LABORATORIO ENERGIA AMBIENTE PIACENZA	LEAP
B2	EU CORE CONSULTING SRL	EUCORE
B3	ENERGEAN OIL & GAS	ENERG-EL
AE3.1	ENERGEAN ITALY SPA	ENERG-IT
B4	BUZZI SPA	BUZZI
AE4.1	DYCKERHOFF CEMENT UKRAINE PRIVATE JOINT-STOCK COMPANY	DY-UA
B5	TITAN CEMENT COMPANY AE	TITAN
B6	SUMITOMO SHI FW ENERGIA OY	SFW
B7	AIR LIQUIDE ITALIA SERVICE SRL	AIL-IT-S
AE7.1	AIR LIQUIDE ITALIA PRODUZIONE SRL	AIL-IT-P
AE7.2	AIR LIQUIDE GLOBAL E&C SOLUTION FRANCE	AIL-F
B8	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV	FRAU
B9	POLITECNICO DI MILANO	POLIMI
B10	THE BOSTON CONSULTING GROUP SRL	BCG
B11	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC
B12	CELITEMENT GMBH & CO. KG	CELIT
B13	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	UU
B14	WIETERSDORFER ALPACEM GMBH	ALCEM
B15	ARTIDEK	ARTIDEK
B16	MTU SHOGENERGY	SHOGen
B17	LAPPEENRANNAN-LAHDEN TEKNILLINEN YLIOPISTO LUT	LUT
B18	TECNO PROJECT INDUSTRIALE SRL	TPI
B19	ASSOCIAZIONE CLUST-ER ENERGIA E SVILUPPO SOSTENIBILE	ClustER
B20	CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING FONDATION	CRES
B21	A2A AMBIENTE SPA	A2AAMB
B22	ENI SPA	ENI
B23	A2A SPA	A2ASpA

1 INTRODUCTION

The HERCCULES "Dissemination and Communication Package" (DCP, D10.2) deliverable compiles all dissemination and communication materials and activities completed during the first reporting period (M1-M18) of the project.

As far as the materials are concerned, this report includes the logo, promotional materials (such as brochure, posters, folders, etc), templates, website structure, social media accounts, publications, press releases and newsletters. All of them have been produced by EUCORE (leader of WP10) with the support of LEAP (Coordinator) and inputs from all the partners. These were written in English and, the brochure is going to be translated into some of the consortium members languages: Italian, Greek, German, Finnish, Spanish, Dutch, Ukrainian and Estonian.

All the materials detailed in this document were produced in accordance with the procedures and project visual identity of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D10.1) submitted in M6.

In addition, this report presents a summary of all the activities performed: dissemination events where HERCCULES participated, publications, communication activities, participation in external events and liaison activities.

The majority of the materials and activities were initially agreed in the project Grant Agreement and D10.1, nevertheless, to increase the opportunities of HERCCULES diffusion, further promotional materials - not originally foreseen- were developed, these are stickers, business cards and postcards.

As a result, the deliverable is a reflection of the work done by all project partners in support of WP10, since dissemination and communication are regarded as strategic activities to engage all the target groups relevant to HERCCULES: Research and scientific community, industrial stakeholders, policymakers, regulatory organizations, press and general public.

While this deliverable thoroughly outlines all the developed Dissemination & Communication materials, channels and events, its primary goal is to assemble a "Communication Package" featuring resources and a summary of outreach efforts. It does not serve as an assessment of these endeavours, as they will be addressed in the Technical report (part B) of the first reporting period (RP1) which will include KPI's and event participant numbers.

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2 LOGO

The final logo (displayed in Figure 1) was selected by the consortium among several proposed options in April 2023 and includes the following concepts:

- i. the slightly modified name of the Greek warrior, to recall the CCUS concept at the core of the project;
- ii. the image of the hero's strength and tenacity connected to the objectives of the project (capture and store the CO₂).

In particular, the logo symbolises HERCCULES, who – after having captured CO₂ in his powerful hands – squeezes it underground, as he was somehow accomplishing his 'Thirteenth Fatigue' for the benefit of modern times: fighting greenhouse gas emissions!

It has three versions (see figures below): with and without a pay-off, vertical and horizontal. The selected sentence for the pay-off is "full CCUS chain demonstration", which is the core objective expected from the project implementation.

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Fig. 1_HERCCULES logo vertical with pay-off (upper-L), vertical without pay-off (upper-R) and horizontal (bottom)

The logo must be used in all the project outputs whenever possible (e.g., leaflets, roll-ups, infographics, newsletters, deliverables, social media, websites, publications, and materials for internal and external events) according to the indications included in the Logo user manual, which is available on the project shared repository and which has been shared with all consortium members. The manual

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specifies the typography that needs to be used, the exact colour Pantone, measures, and how to proceed with different background colours (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2_Procedures on how to use the Logo extracted from the Logo user manual

In addition to the logo, it is of the utmost importance that any project output intended for dissemination and communication (even if performed through electronic means) includes the following text:

"Funded by the European Union. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101096691. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them" and display the EU emblem".

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. The EU emblem can be displayed either with or without pay-off, as indicated in the figure to follow.

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Fig. 3_EU Emblem

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3 TEMPLATES

Three templates have been prepared following the visual identity of the project, in order to harmonise the way HERCCULES is presented: Report, PowerPoint template and General report (either public or confidential):

Report: to be used mainly for public and sensitive deliverables

Fig. 4_HERCCULES Report template

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PowerPoint template: to be used for all project presentations

Fig. 5_HERCCULES Power point presentation template

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General report: for presenting other types of documents not strictly related to the project, such as Policy briefs or liaison activities.

Fig. 6_HERCCULES General Report template

4 PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

A series of promotional materials were designed during the first reporting period following the creation of the visual identity of the project with the aim of strengthening the impact of the HERCCULES D&C campaigns. In particular: brochure, block notes, folder, post cards, business card, template for event's invitation, roll-up and stickers, as described below:

Flyer/Brochure

HERCCULES' brochure has been designed as a tri-fold with a measurement of A4 when open. It describes the main project information, goals, technology, demonstration sites, structure of the consortium and contact details.

The English brochure has been made available to all project partners for download in either printable or web versions. Translations are currently being produced in 8 different languages (Italian, Greek, German, Finnish, Spanish, Dutch, Ukrainian and Estonian) and will be finished within the next months.

Fig. 7_Brochure front/ back and internal pages

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Block notes

The block notes have been designed following the colour palette of the project and they are available to be downloaded and printed in two versions, either striped or checkered:

Fig. 8_Block Notes cover and internal pages

Folder

The folder, useful to be presented on conferences and events, includes all the partners logos and summary of HERCCULES' main information and goals.

Fig. 9_Folder front and back

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Post cards

Three different versions of postcards have been designed, the first one displaying the project solutions; the second one is a figurative representation of the consortium while the third one provides a short description of the project.

Fig.10_Postcards front and back

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Business card

A business card has been created with the purpose of having a small presentation of the project in hand for every occasion. It includes the main information of HERCCULES, the QR codes to the website and social media accounts.

Fig. 11_Business Card front and back

Template for event's invitation

A template for event's invitation has been designed in the [Canva platform](#). It is ready to be modified according to the event by adding other partners logos (in case of liaison activities), title of the event, photo, agenda, description and link. The template has been used for creating the invitation of the First Dissemination event held in Tallinn, Estonia on June 13th, 2024.

Fig. 12_Template for events invitation and example of the invitation for the First Dissemination workshop

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Roll-up

A roll-up, expected to be printed in a measure of 2 m tall and 80 cm wide has been produced. It includes the main information of the project, goals, technology, photos of the demonstration sites, map of the consortium partners, website and social media accounts. It has been created to showcase the project at the First Dissemination Event in Tallinn.

Fig.13_HERCCULES roll-up

Poster

The intention behind creating the project poster was to boost brand recognition for both internal and external events. Although it can be printed in various dimensions, the objective is to make it easier to carry while being more compact and lightweight compared to the project roll-up.

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Fig.14. HERCCULES Poster

Sticker set

A set of 3 stickers has been designed in order to be attached to small gadgets (like cups or bottles, to laptops, bicycles, windows, cars, etc.). They are a good way of promoting the project in other places apart from work/office.

Fig.15. Stickers

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Overview

This overview has been prepared with the aim of having an homogeneous powerpoint presentation to be used by all the partners – without further authorizations from the consortium - in meetings and conferences to introduce the project.

The figure displays six slides from the HERCCULES project overview presentation. The slides are as follows:

- Slide 1: Project overview** - Title slide with HERCCULES logo, date 'Milano xx/xx/2023', and speaker information.
- Slide 2: INDEX** - Table of contents listing sections 1 through 9, including Summary & Numbers, Structure, Timeline, and various innovation actions.
- Slide 3: 1. Summary & Numbers** - Overview of the project's goals, including 'HERCCULES: HEROES IN SOUTHERN EUROPE TO DECARBONIZE INDUSTRY WITH CCUS' and key statistics like '23 partners + 4 affiliated' and 'Budget total: € 39.627.208,00'.
- Slide 4: 2. Structure** - Organizational chart showing the project's structure and key milestones.
- Slide 5: 3. Timeline (I)** - Timeline from 2023 to 2027, highlighting 'Process feasibility, design and development of 1st pilot'.
- Slide 6: 3. Timeline (II)** - Timeline from 2023 to 2027, highlighting 'Experimental testing of 1st pilot'.
- Slide 7: 3. Timeline (III)** - Timeline from 2023 to 2027, highlighting 'Scale-up of 1st pilot'.
- Slide 8: 3. Timeline (VI)** - Timeline from 2023 to 2027, highlighting 'Purification & Refinement of 1st pilot'.

Fig.16_Overview Powerpoint presentation

5 WEBSITE

The HERCCULES project website (www.herccules.eu) was launched on July 2023 (M7) following the project’s visual identity. It has been built upon Concipio platform, a content management system (CMS) and it offers a responsive access for tablets and smartphones.

The website is written in English and it is regularly updated by EUCORE (main administrator of the website), with LEAP’s support and with inputs from all partners. Specific arrangements have already been made to ensure that it will be kept updated after the project conclusion for at least five years.

HERCCULES website has been structured along a public and a private area, whose contents are described in what follows:

a) Public Area:

The website Public Area has been designed in such a way to be the main entry point for sharing information on core project activities and public materials to all main target groups and public at large. It displays key information on the project partners, aims, expected impacts, public deliverables and events. In addition to this, the website has been enriched with a ‘News and Events’ section, to be regularly updated, especially in occasion of the achievement of important technical milestones and of major dissemination events. Links to the project’s social media accounts and a contact form to allow stakeholders to interact with the consortium are also included in the website.

The Public Area is designed as follows:

Page/Feature	Mission	Content
Homepage	Get people to know the main vision of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project name and pay-off • Images of the demonstration sites • HERCCULES in a nutshell • Top News • Partners logos • Subscribe to the Newsletter • Follow us on Social Media
About HERCCULES	Establish credibility Share project background Explain who is involved and how	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project overview • Objectives • Expected impacts • Who we are (Consortium) • Collaboration with other CCUS projects • Demonstration sites
Our work	Provide an overview of the main activities and structure of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work packages
Results & Publications	Public dissemination of project results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverables • Scientific publications • Press

<p>News & Events</p>	<p>Update the public on events that the consortium is organising and attending. Share the latest news concerning the progress and the visibility on social media of the project</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calendar • News • Social wall
<p>Contact</p>	<p>Allow page visitors to contact the consortium</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact form

Table 1_HERCCULES Public Area structure

The *Homepage* (Figure 17) displays a user-friendly access to all the sections, 5 rotating images of the demonstration sites, the main information of the project including the logos of all the partners, the Top News of the moment in a green bar, access to the newsletter subscription and contact information. It also provides the links to the project social media accounts (LinkedIn, Instagram and Twitter).

Fig. 17. Homepage of the Website

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The 'About HERCCULES' section includes a thorough explanation of the project's methodology, main objectives, the composition of all the consortium including a map, a description of each partner and a link to their website, a general overview of the collaboration with other CCUS projects in the regions and finally a brief description of the five demonstration sites.

Fig.18_Project overview (L) and Consortium composition (R)

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Collaboration With Other CCUS Project

PUBLIC PERCEPTION AND BUSINESS MODELS JOINT EVENT - 14th November 2023, Brussels
 Organized by the Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS) & Alternative Fuels Horizon 2020 European Cluster project. Supported by CINEA - European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency.

DISSEMINATION EVENT ON CO2 CAPTURE, TRANSPORT, USE AND STORAGE (CCUS) - June, 13th 2024, Tallinn, Estonia.
 Organized by the company SHGEnergy and the Tallinn Department of Geology. In representation of HERCCULES and CCUS ZEN projects.

OTHER RELEVANT PROJECTS RELATED TO CCUS IN THE INDUSTRY

- Calypso** is a European project granted under Horizon Europe framework programme. The main goal is to act as enabling tool to achieve by 2025 commercial deployment of Calcium looping technology (CAL) using Circulating Fluidised Bed reactors. Three pilot plants will be used in Germany, Sweden and Spain to demonstrate ~99% CO2 capture rates in three hard-to-abate industrial sectors: cement, steel and waste to energy. <https://www.calypso.eu/>
- CAU** is a project funded by the EU H2020 MSCA (88446). This project spans demonstration of two packed bed capture technologies for capital integration into an existing steel plant. CAC develops the Ca-Lo looping technology, involving sorption enhanced water gas shift of the CO contained in Blast Furnace Gases to produce H2 while capturing the CO2 as CaCO3, with regeneration of the CaO sorbent using CaO/Cu chemical loop. <https://www.icaloop.eu/>
- ACCESS** is a four-year Horizon 2020 project that aims to demonstrate technologies and produce tools and plans that enable independent CCS deployment in Europe. <https://www.access-eu.eu/>
- CCUS ZEN** enables knowledge sharing between different stakeholders and between European regions to support full chain development of CCUS by drawing on learnings from ongoing and past projects. CCUS ZEN aims to build a coherent ecosystem of CCUS actors capable of decarbonising Europe's industry and delivering the European Union's climate target plan. <https://www.ccuszen.eu/>
- HERCORD** is a world's first HERCCORD will demonstrate a 100t CO2 capture plant using Rotating Packed Bed (RPB) absorber and desorber with the novel CO2min solvent. <https://hercord.eu/>
- PHOSTRATCO** is investigating geological CO2 storage sites in industrial regions of Southern and Eastern Europe to support development of large scale carbon capture and storage (CCS). <https://phostratco.eu/>
- COMET** is an ambitious initiative that aims to accelerate the transition to a slow carbon future by demonstrating key technologies for the entire CCS value chain in Southern Europe and supporting the development of CCS-ready large emitters with storage sites in Central Eastern Europe.

Demonstration sites

Prinos, Greece
 Prinos Complex, near Argos Sea. Oldest sea hydrocarbon producing asset that will host the first CO2 storage project in the East Mediterranean.

Milan (MI), Italy
 The TIGR 2 waste-to-energy plant is located in the north-west area of Milan and represents a perfect example of a circular economy. In fact, the combustion process generates steam to produce electricity and heat for the district heating system of the city and neighboring municipalities. The plant was commissioned in 2007 and is capable of treating over 300,000 tons of waste per year. In 2022, the plant had approximately 95% CO2 of electricity and the national electricity grid, equal to the annual energy consumption of approximately 100,000 households.

Thessaloniki, Greece
 The TIGR 2 waste-to-energy plant was founded in 1992. Since the new production line was opened in 2022, the TIGR 2 waste-to-energy plant is one of the most advanced incineration units in Europe, with state-of-the-art equipment, high-quality products for sustainable

Prinos, Greece

Venosa (PC), Italy
 Venosa is a cement plant that was founded in 1966 (Piemonte, Italy) in 1966, a new production line was built. As a result, the plant has a maximum capacity of 2,000,000 tonnes. The Venosa plant meets the highest European and international standards. In 2022, a new facility was built on the site of the existing plant, with the construction of the first production line for CO2 capture plant, under the name **HERCCORD**. It is intended for the following year, before the end of the current design generated in the current production process.

- High-capacity cement plant (100,000 tonnes per year)
- Quality System Certification ISO 9001 since 1992 (EN 142)
- Environmental System Certification ISO 14001 since 1992 (EN 14001)
- Occupational Safety and Health Certification OHSAS 18001 since 2003 (EN 18001)
- Environmental Product Declaration (EPD)

Ravenna (RA), Italy
 HERCCORD project

Fig.19_Collaboration with other CCUS projects (L), Demonstration sites (R)

The section 'Our Work' provides an in-depth explanation and description of the Project's Work Package and the activities to be implement.

Fig.20_Work Packages structure and description

In the 'Results and Publication' section, all the public information is displayed and available for download, such as the latest public Deliverables, and the scientific and press publications. In addition, the viewer can access to the abstracts of the sensitive deliverables. It is important to mention that all the public contents of the HERCCULES project are collected in the trusted repository "HERCCULES Community" on Zenodo. Given that some files may be too large to be stored on the website, they are exclusively uploaded into Zenodo, with only a link provided on the corresponding page of the website.

Fig. 21_Results and Publication section

All the main news and events of the project can be easily found within the 'News & Events' section, which includes a Calendar to keep track of the important dates. Here, a Social wall is also displayed where all the posts related to HERCCULES from the three different social media are presented in one page for a better view.

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Fig. 22_ Social wall, News and Events section of the website

Fig.23_ Contact section

The 'Contact' area allows stakeholders and general Public to interact with the consortium by giving the possibility to write a question/comment choosing between the different fields: Cement/ EfW/ Policy/ CO₂ transport/ CO₂ utilization/ CO₂ storage and Other.

Lastly, the 'Newsletter' section allows the visitors to download the previous newsletters and subscribe to receive the future ones.

Fig.24_ Newsletter section

b) Partner Area (private area)

The Partner Area, is exclusively accessible to consortium members with a username and password and it serves as a shared repository for the final documents of HERCCULES:

- Budget/Finances
- Dissemination & Communication materials: including the latest versions of the logo, promotional material, templates, consent forms
- Contracts: in particular Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement;
- Deliverables and Milestones: differentiating between approved, rejected and submitted
- EC reporting.
- Project meetings.

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Fig.25_Partner Area of the website

6 PUBLICATIONS

All the consortium members contributions in the First Reporting Period in peer-review scientific publication, thesis, conference papers and abstracts are summarized in the table to follow.

#	Date and Partner(s) Involved	Type	Title an Author(s)	PID	Journal/ Conferences	Open Access
1	19/07/23 EUCORE and LEAP	Journal Article	<i>Cosa sta facendo l'Europa per la decarbonizzazione del settore industriale? L'esempio di HERCCULES</i> <i>M. Fantini, M. Gatti, M. Spinelli, E. De Lena</i>	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8202404	FEDERBETON	Yes
2	11/2023 EUCORE, LEAP, POLIMI, BUZZI and TPI	Journal Article	<i>Cement sector decarbonisation: a HERCCULEan task?</i> <i>M. Fantini (EU CORE), E. De Lena, M. Spinelli, (LEAP), S. Consonni, M. Gatti, M. C. Romano (POLIMI), M. Katsiotis, V. Michalis (TITAN), F. Canonico, F. Magli (BUZZI), M. Iorio, U. Moretti (TPI)</i>	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10696074	International Cement review (ICR)	Yes
3	07/2023 SFW	Article	<i>TECHNICAL REPORT STATE OF THE ART: CCS TECHNOLOGIES 2023</i>		Global CCS Institute Publication	Yes

Table 2_ HERCCULES Publications during RP1

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Journal article: "What is Europe doing towards Industrial Decarbonisation? The example of HERCCULES"

It was published on **Federbeton magazine** (Confederation of Italian Industry: the Associations of the cement, concrete, manufactured products, components and structures for construction, applications and related technologies). The authors were Martina Fantini (EU CORE), Manuele Gatti (POLIMI), Edoardo De Lena (LEAP) and Maurizio Spinelli (LEAP).

It's written in Italian and available in English upon request. The complete article is available in our Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/records/8204516>

Fig 26_ Cover of the article

Journal article: Cement sector decarbonisation: an HERCCULEan task?

Partners from HERCCULES project M. Fantini (EUCORE Consulting), E. De Lena, S. Consonni, M. Gatti, M.C. Romano, M. Spinelli (LEAP/Polimi), M. Katsiotis, V. Michalis, N. Diamantonis (TITAN), F. Canonico, F. Magli (BUZZI), M. Iorio and U. Moretti (TPI), have written an article that was published in the prestigious **INTERNATIONAL CEMENT REVIEW (ICR)** magazine, edition November 2023.

The article gives insight on HERCCULES' aim to accelerate the scale-up of CCUS technologies in Mediterranean Europe, demonstrating the feasibility of the entire CO₂ CCUS value chain with a focus on energy-environmental performance, safety, optimisation of CO₂ logistics, and economic and social acceptability aspects.

The complete article is available in our Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/records/10696074>

Fig 27_First page of the article

7 PROJECT DISSEMINATION EVENTS

As agreed in the GA, during the First Reporting Period, HERCCULES has organized 2 Dissemination events:

1) KICK-OFF Meeting – Piacenza, Italy (February 15th and 16th 2023)

On the 15th and 16th of February, 2023 it was organized the project’s Kick-off meeting and first General Assembly where the partners presented the activities foreseen in the following months and had the opportunity to visit the A2A “Silla 2” Waste to Energy plant in Milan where a first-of-a-kind complete Calcium-Looping (CaL) pilot plant (~ 1 MWth size) will be installed.

HERCCULES: HEROES IN SOUTHERN EUROPE TO DECARBONIZE INDUSTRY WITH CCUS

Kick-off Meeting – KoM
February 15th and 16th, 2023
Caserma della Nave - Politecnico - via Sabotini/L 76 - PIACENZA (PC) - ROOM L*
LINK FOR ONLINE ACCESS (WEBEX) PW: Nf8XY73GVuS
<https://pollitecnicoonline.webex.com/join?URL=1441471121541046400008>

Agenda
15th February, 2023

Time	Topic	Speaker
9:00-9:30	Arrival	
9:30-9:50	Welcome by the Coordinator, project overview	LEAP
9:50-10:50	Round table (first half – entities ordered as in the proposal)	all
10:50-11:20	Coffee break	
11:20-12:20	Round table (second half)	all
12:20-13:00	Presentation by the PO	Maria MORALES CANOVAS - CINEA
13:00-14:50	Press conference and lunch	
14:50-15:25	WP1: Project Management and quality control	LEAP-Eurocre
15:25-16:15	WP2: Demonstration at TR7-S and optimization of the hybrid CO ₂ capture technology in two cement plants	TITAN
16:15-16:55	WP3: Demonstration at TR7-S and optimization of the Calcium Looping pilot in an Energy-from-Waste plant	ADA
16:55-17:30	Coffee break	
17:30-18:00	WP4: CO ₂ utilization & resource circularity	BLAZZ
18:00-18:40	WP5: Demonstration at TR8 of sustainable and safe CO ₂ storage in Italy and Greece, including permitting, logistics and scalability	ENI
18:40-19:00	WP6: Business and financial aspects and sustainable assessment for the full CCUS chain	BCG

20:30 - Dinner – Grande Albergo Roma (Piacenza)

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HERCCULES: HEROES IN SOUTHERN EUROPE TO DECARBONIZE INDUSTRY WITH CCUS

Kick-off Meeting – KoM
February 15th and 16th, 2023
Caserma della Nave - Politecnico - via Sabotini/L 76 - PIACENZA (PC) - ROOM L*
LINK FOR ONLINE ACCESS (WEBEX) PW: Nf8XY73GVuS
<https://pollitecnicoonline.webex.com/join?URL=1441471121541046400008>

Agenda
16th February, 2023

Time	Topic	Speaker
8:30-8:45	Arrival	
8:45-9:20	WP6: Optimal design of the integrated CCUS chain, including transportation, for Southern European industrial clusters	UIJ
9:20-10:00	WP7: Exploitation towards first-of-a-kind full-scale industrial projects	AIL
10:00-10:30	Coffee break	
10:30-11:30	WP8: Social perception and community engagement	FRAU
11:30-12:00	Session: Trans- and interdisciplinary dialogue	
12:00-12:30	WP10: Communication, dissemination and knowledge sharing	EUCCORE
12:30-13:00	Lunch	
13:00-17:00	Visit to A2A Silla 2 Waste to Energy plant in Milan	
13:00-14:00	Bus Shuttle will leave at 13:00 from Politecnico, the journey will take about an hour	
14:15-15:45	Plant Visit	
16:00-17:00	Bus Shuttle will leave at 16:00 from Silla2, the journey will take about an hour	

*Times are expressed in CET - Central European Time

Notes:
- The meeting and the press conference will take place in rooms L;
- Lunch buffet and coffee breaks will be served in rooms L;
(indications of the classrooms will be posted on the walls of Politecnico)

Funded by the European Union
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101016466. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate Action and Innovation Executive Agency (ECAIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Fig.28_Agenda of the Kick-off meeting

Fig.29_Group photo of the consortium during the Kick-off meeting

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2) HERCCULES' First Dissemination Workshop – Tallinn, Estonia (June 13th 2024)

DISSEMINATION EVENT ON CO₂ CAPTURE, TRANSPORT, USE AND STORAGE (CCUS) - June, 13th 2024, Tallinn, Estonia.

Organised by the company SHOGenergy and the TalTech Department of Geology, in representation of HERCCULES and CCUS ZEN projects, respectively.

The event has started at 9:00 with a welcome coffee followed by two introductory timeslots dedicated to presenting the two projects co-organizing the event, their latest results and upcoming activities. Then, the participants had the opportunity to deepen some crucial themes such as the CO₂ capture in Waste-to-Energy plants (A2A and TPI- HERCCULES) together with the future scenarios of the infrastructures for transport and storage (ENI - HERCCULES). Key presentations included the techno-economic modelling of the Baltic CCUS Scenario (Rambol-CCUS ZEN) and the analysis of the value chain scenarios in the Baltic and Mediterranean Regions (TalTech-CCUS ZEN).

The last session of the event was dedicated to the regulations, public acceptance and policies issues (IOM LAW- CCUS ZEN; Fraunhofer ISI - HERCCULES), with a panel discussion involving HERCCULES and CCUS ZEN experts, networking partners and local stakeholders. The panel discussion has covered a full range of CCUS issues presented during the day.

The event has been a hub for stakeholders, policymakers, industry representatives, and researchers to engage in a constructive dialogue on key issues in the field.

Take away messages, Public slides, Flyer and Agenda are available for download in our Zenodo community: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12570378.

Time	Topic	Speaker
09:00 - 09:30	Registration of the participants and coffee	
09:30 - 11:00	Session 1: Introduction of Horizon Europe projects and CCUS technology Co-Chairman: Martina Fanti (EUROPE-HERCCULES)	
09:30 - 10:00	Introduction to Horizon Europe HERCCULES project	Maurizio Spinelli, Project Coordinator (SHOG)
10:00 - 10:30	Introduction to Horizon Europe CCUS ZEN project	Rasmus Vignier (SCCS - CCUS ZEN)
10:30 - 11:00	CO ₂ Capture in Waste to Energy plants	Adriano Carone (A2A SGA-HERCCULES)
11:00 - 13:00	Session 2: CCUS projects and future scenarios Co-Chairman: Pierre-Georges SIFFERT (CCUS ZEN)	
11:30 - 12:00	Infrastructures for the transport and storage Co-Chairman: Leandro-Henrique Soares (Rambol-CCUS ZEN)	Ruberto Ferrero (ENI - HERCCULES)
12:00 - 12:30	Techno-economic modelling of the Baltic CCUS Scenario (Denmark, Sweden & Germany)	Leandro-Henrique Soares (Rambol-CCUS ZEN)
12:30 - 13:00	Analysis of the value chain scenarios in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions	Alii Shogomov (TalTech-CCUS ZEN)
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 16:00	Session 3: Regulations, public acceptance and policies Co-Chairman: Aida Shogomova (TalTech-CCUS ZEN, SHOGenergy-HERCCULES)	
14:00 - 14:25	Regulatory aspects: Obstacles/barriers to overcome	Luigi De Dominicis (IOM LAW - CCUS ZEN) online
14:25 - 14:50	Public acceptance and the role and the potential contribution of the policy makers	Anne Kemmler (Fraunhofer ISI - HERCCULES)

- The HERCCULES project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101034601. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Investment Executive Agency (ECIIIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.
- The CCUS ZEN project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101034608.
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14:50 - 15:15	CCS Developments in the Baltic States	Janis Valters (Bellona - Estonia)
15:15 - 16:15	Panel discussion involving CCUS ZEN networking partners, HERCCULES and local stakeholders	Anne Kemmler (Fraunhofer ISI - HERCCULES) Alii Shogomov (TalTech-CCUS ZEN) Martina Fanti (EUROPE-HERCCULES)
16:15 - 16:30	Wrap-up session	
16:30 - 17:15	Farewell Coffee	

*Timing may be adjusted to local time (UTC+2)

Registration link to the Dissemination event:
<https://forms.office/P93TXU2mcWomcyX8?>

EU Horizon Europe project CCUS ZEN
Zero Emission Network to facilitate CCUS uptake in the industry
<https://www.ccuszen.eu/>

HERCCULES
EU Horizon Europe project
HEROES IN SOUTHERN EUROPE TO DECARBONIZE INDUSTRY WITH CCUS
<https://www.herccules.eu/>

Fig.30_Flyer of the Dissemination event and Agenda

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Fig.31_Photos of the First Dissemination event

8 PARTICIPATION IN EXTERNAL EVENTS

The following table contains a summary of the partners' participation on external events during the RP1:

#	Partners Involved	Activity name & Description	Type of Activity	Date	Location	Target audience reached
1	ClusterER, EUCORE, LEAP	HERCCULES presentation to RER	Meeting	13/03/23	Online	Policy makers
2	LEAP	Presentation of HERCCULES project at HTSLC	Conference	29/03/23	Piacenza, Italy	Research communities; Industry, business partners; Innovators; Investors.
3	ClusterER, EUCORE, LEAP	HERCCULES presentation to Tenaris	Meeting	05/05/23	Online	Industry
4	LEAP	Presentation of HERCCULES project at IETS TCP's International Conference	Conference	10/05/23	Gothenburg, Sweden	Research communities; Industry, business partners; Innovators; Investors
5	ENERG-EL	Present the Prinos CCS project as a decarbonization option for SE Europe	Conference	31/05/23	Athens, Greece	Research Communities
6	LEAP	"Carbon-free energy recovery from waste", Keynote presentation introducing HERCCULES, at MATER meeting	Conference	06/06/23	Piacenza, Italy	Research communities; Industry, business partners; Innovators; Investors
7	ClusterER	HERCCULES presentation and updates to Cluster Greentech associates	Meeting	27/06/23	Fusignano, Italy	Industrial, business partners
8	ClusterER, LEAP, EUCORE	HERCCULES project presentation to Cluster-ER Greentech's associate Rosetti Marino Group	Meeting	24/07/23	Online	Industrial, business partners
9	SFW	Presentation of the HERCCULES project at Cemtech	Education and training event	06/09/23	Online	Industrial, business partners
10	LEAP	"Techno-economic comparison between solvent-based, hybrid and integrated Ca-Looping processes for	Conference	27/09/23	Pittsburgh, USA	Research Communities

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#	Partners Involved	Activity name & Description	Type of Activity	Date	Location	Target audience reached
		post-combustion CO ₂ capture in cement plants" Oral presentation, PCCC7 Conference				
11	SFW	Presentation of the HERCCULES project at the Carbon Capture Technology Expo 2023	Conference	27-28/09/23	Bremen, Germany	Industrial, business partners
12	FRAU	CCS social science research - Networking telcon. HERCCULES project presentation	Meeting	04/10/23	Online (Karlsruhe)	Research communities
13	ClustER	HERCCULES Project presentation at OMC	Conference	25/10/23	Ravenna, Italy	Industrial, business partners
14	LEAP	"Unlocking the CCUS deployment in Southern Europe: challenges and lessons learned from CLEANKER and HERCCULES pioneer projects" 50° Totem Meeting, IFRF	Conference	05/12/23	Piacenza, Italy	Industrial, business partners
15	ClustER and LEAP	First Regional Stakeholders committee - Italy (activity from WP8)	Meeting	16/01/24	Bologna, Italy	Industry, regional authority, research and civil society
16	ClustER, EUCORE, ENI, ENERGIE AN	Meeting about CCUS projects ongoing in the framework of the ecosystem of innovation of Emilia-Romagna region - Italy	Other scientific collaboration	15/02/24	University of Bologna, Italy	Researchers and industrial partners
17	ClustER	Presentation to Brazilian funding agency	Meeting	22/05/24	Bologna, Italy	Policy makers from Brazil (funding agencies), other clust-ERS of Emilia Romagna, Art-ER
18	FRAU	Presentation on public perception of CCUS and the role of policy during the joint dissemination event on CCUS of HERCCULES and CCUS ZEN	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	13/06/24	Tallinn, Estonia	Specific end user communities
19	FRAU	Presentation of HERCCULES project and acceptance results at at Morgenstadt Werkstatt NEO 2024	Workshop	17/06/24	Heilbronn, Germany	Researchers, municipalities, industrial partners

#	Partners Involved	Activity name & Description	Type of Activity	Date	Location	Target audience reached
20	ClustER	Presentation to the board of ClustER	Meeting	17/06/24	Online	9 members from industry and research centers
21	FRAU	Presentation of HERCCULES results and societal pathways to CCUS at IST conference	Conference	19/06/24	Oslo, Norway	Research communities
22	ClustER	Presentation at the Regional Strategic Forum on Blue Economy	Meeting	19/06/24	Bologna (RER), Italy	Policy makers and industry
23	ClustER	Flyers at the stand of the R2B fair (Innovation fair of Emilia Romagna, Italy)	Other	26-27/06/24	Bologna, Italy	
24	ClustER	Presentation during the Assembly	Meeting	26/06/24	Bologna, Italy	About 90 attendees (Industry, research centers, educational centers, universities)
25	CRES	First Regional Stakeholders committee - Greece (activity from WP8)	Meeting	05/06/24	Online	Industry, regional authority, research and civil society

Table 3_ HERCCULES Participation in external events during RP1

First Regional Stakeholder Committee – Italy (Bologna - Italy, January 16th 2024)

As part of the “Social Perception and Community Engagement” work package, HERCCULES partner ClustER Greentech, organised the first regional stakeholder committee that took place in Bologna, Italy on January 16th, 2024.

This meeting has provided a platform for exchange between local representatives from different areas of society such as research, industry, policy and interested associations. Around 30 stakeholders attended the meeting and were divided into 4 groups following the 4-helix (civil society, government, academic and industry)

More information, full Executive Summary and photos available in our Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/records/12532133>

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Fig.32_ Cluster and LEAP at the First Regional stakeholder committee

Fig.33_ Executive Summary of the First Regional stakeholder committee - Italy

First Regional Stakeholder Committee – Greece (Online, June 5th 2024)

In addition to the above activity, and also as part of the WP8, the Regional Stakeholder Committee was also held in Greece, organized by the partner CRES. It was performed online and it included an introduction of the CRES team working in the HERCCULES project, a presentation of other ongoing European CCUS projects and finished with an interesting discussion among the partners and the stakeholders.

Fig.34_ Photos from the First Regional stakeholder committee - Greece

9 LIAISON ACTIVITIES

The following liaison activities were performed during the First Reporting Period:

a) **CCUS ZEN Project meeting - Copenhagen, Denmark (March, 7-8th 2023).**

During the CCUS ZEN hybrid project Meeting in Copenhagen on March 7th and 8th, 2023, Martina Fantini from EUCORE presented the Horizon Europe HERCCULES project to the CCUS ZEN's 15 partners and 50 different networking partners (including research communities, industry and business).

Fig. 35_HERCCULES presentation within CCUS ZEN project workshop

b) **Joint event on “Public Perception and Business Models” - Brussels, Belgium (November 14th 2023).**

The event was organized by the Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS) & Alternative Fuels Horizon 2020/ Horizon Europe Cluster Projects and supported by CINEA. Public perception and business models are key to enabling innovative technologies, guiding the decisions of the policymakers at national and European Commission levels. In addition, more and more Horizon calls require these two aspects to be dealt with in relation to the technology that will be developed in the project.

Fig.36_ Martina Fantini (EUCORE) presents HERCCULES project at the Joint Event "Public perception and Business Model", Brussels, November 2023

With more than 20 selected Horizon projects and more than 50 key stakeholders involved in the audience, this joint workshop has represented a unique opportunity to strongly impact both on the activities still to be implemented by the ongoing projects and the design of new projects at higher TRL (close to commercial scale). Bringing together stakeholders from various technical projects has provided an excellent networking opportunity for policymakers, building relationships with industry experts, project representatives, investors and policy makers, thus facilitating collaboration, knowledge sharing, and future partnerships.

HERCCULES, together with eCOCO2, CLEANKER and CaLby2030 projects have co-organized the event.

Martina Fantini from EUCORE chaired the session on "Public perception" and, together with Jose Serra from eCOCO2 project, have presented an overview of the workshop and have provided the concluding remarks.

Elisabeth Duetschke from FRAU has given the presentation for HERCCULES and chair the « Public perception emerging issues» session.

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Funded by the European Union	
14th November 2023, Brussels Rue du Trône 62, 1050 Ixelles, Belgium CSC Room 3, 7th floor	
Agenda	
9:00 - 9:30	Registration
9:30 - 9:35	Welcome and workshop overview Jose Serra, Martina Fontes (on behalf of eCOCO2 & CLEANER/CALBY2030/HERCCULES)
9:35 - 9:40	CINEA Introduction Speaker - Maria Marques Canovas
Session 1: Public Perception	
Chair: Martina	
9:40 - 9:50	Case Study - CAU Speaker: Vincent de Gooijert
9:50 - 10:00	Case Study - ACCES3 Speaker: Sanchez Berbegal, Jose Alberto
10:00 - 10:10	Case Study - ConsenCUS Speaker: Joe Morrison
10:10 - 10:20	Case Study - Calby2030 Speaker: Jose L. Ovejero
10:20 - 10:30	Case Study - FOSTRATEGY and HERCCULES Speaker: Elisabeth Duestchke
10:35 - 10:45	Case Study - eCOCO2 Speaker: Linda Engelmann
10:45 - 10:55	Case study - MOF4Air Speaker: Sayra Korytas
10:55 - 11:30	Coffee Break
11:30 - 11:40	Case Study - Sun-To-X Speaker: Jonas Pigeon
11:40 - 11:50	Case study - 3D Speaker: Laila Tröls
11:50 - 12:05	Case Study - NEGEM and AURORA Speaker: David Reiner
12:05 - 12:15	Case Study - CO2BRANDS Speaker: Imke Hovenkämper
12:15 - 12:25	Case study - CO2Fokus Speaker: Adriana Diaz
12:25 - 12:40	Case Study - DigMon & BioNET Speaker: Danny Otto
12:40 - 12:55	Q&A
12:55 - 14:00	Lunch

Funded by the European Union	
Session 2: Business Models	
Chair: Jose	
14:00 - 14:10	Case study - CAU Speaker: Henrik Galbraith-Olive
14:10 - 14:20	Case study - GICO Speaker: Chiara Lurano
14:20 - 14:30	Case study - 3D Speaker: Paolo Coussy
14:30 - 14:40	Case study - VIVALDI Speaker: Jorge Senan Salinas (BETA Technological Center) and Elvira Serra (Ile Skills)
14:40 - 14:55	Q&A
14:55 - 15:15	Short Break
End-of-day summary	
Chair	
15:15 - 15:30	Summary of issues emerging in case studies for Session 1 Rapporteur: Elisabeth Duestchke
15:30 - 15:45	Summary of issues emerging in case studies for Session 2 Rapporteur: Enrico Bocci
15:45 - 16:00	Formalisation/Agreeing on the major challenges Rapporteur: Laura Almar
16:00 - 16:10	Concluding remarks and greeting Speaker: Jose and Martina
16:10 - 16:45	Coffee Break
17:00	End

Fig.37_Agenda of the "Public perception and Business Models Joint event"

The complete Report is available in our Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/records/10636402>

Fig 38_Public Perception and Business Models Joint event Report

c) **HERCCULES project presentation during [ENCASE project](#) meeting - Piacenza, Italy (May 28th and 29th, 2024)**

On May 28th and 29th, 2024, during an ENCASE project meeting held in Piacenza, Italy, Elisa Guasti from Clust-ER Greentech made a presentation of the status of HERCCULES project, with focus on the activities carried out in the WP8 about Social perception, acceptance and citizens engagement.

Fig 39_Photos of HERCCULES presentation during ENCASE project meeting

d) Lastly, the **DISSEMINATION EVENT ON CO₂ CAPTURE, TRANSPORT, USE AND STORAGE (CCUS)** held on June, 13th 2024 in Tallinn, Estonia, would also count as Liaison activity since it was organised by HERCCULES and CCUS ZEN projects.

10 SOCIAL MEDIA

Three social media accounts have been created: LinkedIn (@HERCCULES project), X (former Twitter) (@HERCCULESprojec) and Instagram (@hercculesproject), to connect with general public, stakeholders and disseminate news about the project. X and Instagram were opened in M2 and LinkedIn in M3, and each one has different aims/targets:

- LinkedIn is much more oriented towards professional content and it can be used to establish networks on specific topics;
- Instagram acts mainly as a repository for images and audio-visual content;
- Twitter allows to engage in real-time bidirectional communication with the community and is preferably used to share instant announcements, industry news, comments, opinions, blog content, visual content (such as infographics), news on recent and future events and general tips.

A thorough description of expected number of characters and target audience of each account is detailed on the D&C Plan (D10.1).

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Fig.40_HERCCULES Social media accounts

Posts are expected to be different in each of the accounts, while on [LinkedIn](#) we normally post description of the sites/ specific equipment, hiring positions, results/publications or graphics/simulations about the activities, [Instagram](#) is more focused on photos of the current team, new entries, videos or reels explaining the activities and photos about participation in conferences or presentations. [Twitter](#) on the other hand, is mostly use for sharing instant content such as HERCCULES participation in conferences or another event.

EUCORE is in charge of the overall management of the Social accounts by collecting contributions from all the beneficiaries according to the editorial plan agreed with the consortium (see Annex 2 of the D10.1). The contributions are then transformed with the visual identity of the project and posted. In addition to this, all partners actively contribute by liking the posts, leaving comments, and reposting on their social accounts.

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Fig.41_Examples of social media posts published during the RP1

11 PRESS RELEASES AND OTHER MASS MEDIA

The table below provides a summary of all the communication activities carried out within the first reporting period, including: press releases, articles, social media posts (outside the HERCCULES accounts), mentions on websites, participation on events and appearances on YouTube and television.

#	Activity Name	Description	Date	Communication channel	Target audience reached
1	Project and event launch	LEAP shared a LinkedIn post launching HERCCULES KoM	15/02/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
2	Project and event launch	LEAP shared a LinkedIn post launching HERCCULES during the second day of the KoM	16/02/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
3	Project launch Post	AIR LIQUIDE LinkedIn post in occasion of the Project Kick-off meeting + Sponsorization	16/02/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
4	Project launch Post	AIR LIQUIDE Twitter (X) post in occasion of the Project Kick-off meeting	16/02/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
5	Progetto HERCCULES il sequestro della CO ₂ alla prova del nove	POLIMI did a Radio broadcast on the HERCCULES project ideas, expected results and impacts on Radio 24	16/02/23	TV_Radio_campaign	Civil society Students Researchers
6	Project and event launch	Clust-ER shared a LinkedIn post launching HERCCULES during the the second day of the KoM	16/02/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
7	Project launch activities done by: EUCORE, ENI, AIRLIQUIDE, CLUST-ER, TPI, BUZZI, A2A, ENERGEAN and BCG	Press release and press conference in occasion of HERCCULES KoM	16/02/23	Event	Industry, business partners
		Article at Energiaeoltre	20/02/23	Media Article	Civil society
		Article at ADVFN	16/02/23	Media Article	Civil society
		Article at Canale Energia	15/02/23	Media Article	Civil society
		Article at Corriere di Romagna (Newspaper – Ravenna)	16/02/23	Newspaper	Civil society
		Article at EnergyUp Tech	02/2023	Media Article	Civil society
		Article at Innovation Post	15/02/23	Media Article	Civil society
		Article at Libertà (Newspaper Piacenza)	16/02/23	Newspaper	Civil society
		Article + TV Broadcast at Telelibertà (Piacenza's local TV)	16/02/23	Media Article + TV_Radio_campaign	Civil society
		Article at MarketScreener	02/2023	Media Article	Civil society
		Article at Il sole 24 ore (Italian newspaper)	16/02/23	Newspaper	Civil society
		Article at Piacenza sera	15/02/23	Media Article	Civil society
		Article at PortoRavennaNews	16/02/23	Media Article	Civil society
Article at TGCom24	16/02/23	Media Article	Civil society		
Article at Il resto del Carlino	16/02/23	Media Article	Civil society		

#	Activity Name	Description	Date	Communication channel	Target audience reached
		Article at Oggigreen	17/02/23	Media Article	Civil society
		Article at Staffetta quotidiana	16/02/23	Media Article	Civil society
		Article at Il bollettino	27/02/23	Media Article	Civil society
8	Project Launch	News at POLIMI's Website introducing HERCCULES	16/02/23	Website	Civil society, Research communities
9	Project launch	LEAP published an article at Quotidiano energia introducing the Project after the KoM	16/02/23	Media Article	General Public, Civil society, National and International authorities Industry, business partners
10	Project launch	LEAP published an article at Global Cement introducing the the Project after the KoM	17/02/23	Media Article	General Public, Civil society, National and International authorities Industry, business partners
11	Project launch	News regarding HERCCULES KoM was posted on AIR LIQUIDE's website	20/02/23	Website	Other
12	HERCCULES introduction on X	POLIMI introduced the HERCCULES project in its Twitter (X) account	21/02/23	Social Media	General public, Civil society
13	HERCCULES introduction on LinkedIn	POLIMI introduced the HERCCULES project in its LinkedIn account	23/02/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
14	Project Launch	The Energy Department of POLIMI shared the news introducing the HERCCULES project on its website	28/02/23	Website	Civil society, National and International authorities Industry, business partners
15	Cluste-ER newsletter	Cluste-ER introduces its partnership in HERCCULES	29/03/23	Website	Civil society, Industry, business partners
16	Earth Day	SFW underlines the importance of HERCCULES for the environment on its LinkedIn profiles	24/04/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
17	Presentation Piano di Sviluppo	Description of the development plan designed by Tecnopolo di Piacenza with	26/04/23	Other	Research communities

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#	Activity Name	Description	Date	Communication channel	Target audience reached
	Tecnopolo di Piacenza	respect to the site managed by LEAP			
18	Press Release	AIR LIQUIDE shared HERCCULES Press Release at the Made in Steel fair	9-11/05/23	Event	Civil society, Industry, business partners
19	Speech	Speech of Prof. Consonni (LEAP) at the IREN anniversary in Torino (Italy)	10/05/23	Other	Industry, business partners
20	LinkedIn post	Content publication on LinkedIn about the role of Air Liquide within the project	26/06/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
21	Cluste-ER in HERCCULES	Cluste-ER dedicated a page on its website to introduce HERCCULES project and its role in the implementation of the action	03/08/23	Website	Civil society, National and International authorities Industry, business partners
22	Article: What CCUS is	Cluste-ER published an article explaining what CCUS is and mentioned HERCCULES as one of the projects involved in this technology implementation	08/08/23	Website	Civil society, National and International authorities Industry, business partners
23	Women in CCUS	Cluste-ER shared a post on its LinkedIn profile attesting its attendance to the "Women in CCUS" workshop as member of HERCCULES project	27/09/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
24	Cluste-ER newsletter	HERCCULES project was mentioned in Cluste-ER's newsletter of September 2023	02/10/23	Newsletter	Civil society, Industry, business partners
25	SEO article for the Air Liquide blog	In a blog article dedicated to the topic of the carbon neutrality published on the Air Liquide website, HERCCULES project was mentioned	16/10/23	Website	General public, industry, business partners
26	Cluste-ER LinkedIn post	HERCCULES was tagged in a the Cluste-ER LinkedIn post made in occasion of its participation at the OMC Med Energy Conference Exhibition	26/10/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
27	"SFW's networked R&D drives global decarbonization development"	Media article in SFW website	11/2023	Media Article	Industry, business partners

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#	Activity Name	Description	Date	Communication channel	Target audience reached
28	Cluste-ER newsletter	HERCCULES project was mentioned in Cluste-ER's newsletter of November 2023	01/12/23	Newsletter	Civil society, Industry, business partners
29	AIL-IT-P 2023 sum-up - LinkedIn post	In a carousel on the activities that saw AIR LIQUIDE involved in 2023, the participation in the HERCCULES project was mentioned	21/12/23	Social Media	Industry, business partners
30	ClustER event	Event for 120 ClustER partners from industry (62%, research centers and training centers)	17/01/24	Event	Industrial, business partners
31	Italian Stakeholder Committee LinkedIn post	Clust-ER provided an update on its activities within the HERCCULES project regarding the organization of the first Italian Stakeholder committee	19/01/2024	Social Media	Industry, business partners
32	Cluste-ER newsletter	HERCCULES project was mentioned in Cluste-ER's newsletter of January 2024	31/01/2024	Newsletter	Civil society, Industry, business partners
33	Update of Energean website pages	Website article mentioning HERCCULES on ENERGEAN website	01/03/2024	Website	International Organisation (UN body, OECD, etc) Local authorities National authorities Regional authorities EU institutions civil society Journalists
34	Home coming day - LUT	Alumni event for old students of LUT and employees	13/04/24	Event	Civil society, Others
35	Post LinkedIn Clust-ER	Clust-ER reposted a HERCCULES project LinkedIn post, providing an update regarding its current involvement in WP8	22/04/24	Social Media	Civil society, Industry, business partners
36	News published on the AIL-IT-P website	News published on the Air Liquide Italian website to announce their participation in the GET 2024 event on July 2024	28/05/24	Website	Industry, business partners
37	AIL-IT-P Post on LinkedIn - organic content	Post published on Air Liquide's LinkedIn profile to give	03/06/24	Social Media	Industry, business partners

#	Activity Name	Description	Date	Communication channel	Target audience reached
		visibility to the speeches at GET 2024 + Sponsorization			
38	AIL-IT-P Advertorial article	Article in the specialized online magazine Staffetta Quotidiana to give visibility to the speeches at GET 2024	05/06/24	Media Article	Industry, business partners
39	AIL-IT-P Advertorial article	Article in the specialized online monthly magazine T@day to give visibility to the speeches at GET 2024	12/06/24	Media Article	Industry, business partners

Table 4_ HERCCULES Communication activities during RP1

****5**** In February 2023, the HERCCULES project was the subject of a special broadcast episode on Radio 24-Melis entitled "[Progetto HERCCULES: il sequestro della CO2 alla prova del nove](#)".

Fig 42_Cover of the Radio 24 broadcast

****27** Article: "SFW's networked R&D drives global decarbonization development"**

HERCCULES' partner Sumitomo SHI/FW have published the article entitled "SFW's networked R&D drives global decarbonization development" in which they explained their new solutions for the generation and storage of energy, the valorisation of wastes and residues, and the capture of carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the most carbon-intensive industries, given HERCCULES as one of the examples of funded projects

Link to the article here: [SFW's networked R&D drives global decarbonization development | Sumitomo SHI FW \(shi-fw.com\)](#)

Fig 43_ Sumitomo SHI/FW article

12 NEWSLETTERS

Newsletters are planned on a bi-annual basis, as agreed on the GA.

The **first** one was distributed on November 2023 providing a summary of the activities performed during the first months of the project. It starts with a summary of the kick-off meeting and first General Assembly, held in Piacenza, Italy in February 2023, including a visit to "La Silla 2" Waste to energy plant in Milan where the first-of-a kind complete Calcium-Looping (CaL) will be installed. Then describes HERCCULES broadcasted on the radio and participation in external events, i.e., the CCUS ZEN's project meeting in Copenhagen, the Made in Steel event on May 2023 in Piacenza and the Joint event on 'Public Perception and Business Model' in November 2023. Lastly, the "where we are" section details the deliverables and milestones submitted and a brief description of the coming events.

The **second** newsletter was finalised and sent on May 2024. Following the same structure, it includes a summary of the First Regional Stakeholder committee event organized by HERCCULES in Bologna, on January 2024. In addition, this newsletter included a brief summary of "where we are" on each WP with vibrant photos to illustrate each point. Finally, information regarding the organization of the First Dissemination Event to be held in Tallin was shared.

Both of the newsletters are available to be downloaded from the [website](#).

HERCCULES

full CCUS chain demonstration

Fig.44_ First and Second HERCCULES Newsletter

13 ADDITIONAL COMMUNICATION MATERIAL

During the First Reporting period, two additional activities were addressed:

a) Master Communication Document

Given the complexity of the issues to be tackled on HERCCULES project, partners deemed it imperative to jointly produce a report called “*Master Communication Document*” to be used internally by the consortium for any Dissemination & Communication initiative that might require an input on CCUS and on HERCCULES.

The coordinating group focused on this activity included EUCORE, POLIMI, ClusterER and FRAU.

This Master Document, delves into official data regarding the climate crisis to offer a comprehensive explanation of the technology's significance in the decarbonisation strategy.

Fig.45_ HERCCULES Master Communication Document cover

b) Activity with students at POLIMI School of Design (June 2024)

On June 3rd, 2024, professor Manuele Gatti, Riccardo Cremona and Lia Tagliavini from POLIMI Department of Energy and Martina Fantini from EUCORE participated in an event with Sabrina Scuri and team from POLIMI School of Design.

The aim was to provide knowledge on CCUS to the students of the School of Design for them to develop and create in 5 working days multimedial CCUS content within the framework of their end-of-year project. Nine groups have been formed, each providing different contents (slides, infographic, videos, game, etc.). Students have been assisted by the coordination team including also the support of Prof. Matteo Romano from POLIMI Department of Energy.

On June 7th, 2024, students presented their work and 3 groups have been granted.

More information and complete contents of every group available in our Zenodo community: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12206880

Fig. 46_Manuele Gatti (L) and group photo (R)

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full CCUS chain demonstration

Fig. 47_Infographics designed by the winner group

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